

Some Transition Metal Halide Complexes of Cyanoacetylhydrazide

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Metal complexes of cyanoacetylhydrazide (CAH) were prepared. I.R. spectra of the solid complexes, electronic spectra both in solid phase and in solution, are discussed. This bidentate ligand coordinates through the carbonyl oxygen and the cyanide nitrogen groups. The structure of the solid complexes are discussed.

DURING the progress of this work, two studies have appeared. Zommer¹ in their studies on the spectra of cyanoacetylhydrazide of copper(II), have suggested the "imidol" structure. Paul et al² in their studies on I. R. spectra of titanium and antimony complexes of cyanoacetylhydrazide suggested only the carbonyl oxygen as the coordination site.

The aim of the present investigation is to ascertain by as much evidence as possible the nature and composition of cyanoacetylhydrazide with some metal ions.

Experimental

Material used :

Cyanoacetylhydrazide was prepared by refluxing ethylcyanoacetate with hydrazine³. It was purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol (m.p., 114-115°). All the metal salts used were of AR grade.

Physical measurements :

Spectrophotometric measurements were done in the visible SP. 1800 using 1 cm matched silica and glass cells.

The I.R. spectra of the solid materials were taken in KBr discs using a Pye Unicam SP. 2000 infrared spectrophotometer.

The conductance values were measured using a conductivity cell of the G.M. type dipping in the solution to be titrated, The temperature was adjusted by placing the cell in an ultrathermostat. A Beckman conductivity bridge was employed.

Preparation of the Complexes :

1:1 and 1:2 metal—ligand complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar amounts of the hydrazide and the metal salts in absolute ethanol. The solid complexes filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Analysis of the Complexes :

Halides were determined gravimetrically as silver halide, cobalt as cobalttetrpyridinium dithiocyanate. Cadmium, manganese, and zinc were determined volumetrically by EDTA using Eriochrome black T as indicator. Hydrazine nitrogen was determined as described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

The complexes obtained have the general formula $M(HL)_2 \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Co, Cd, Mn$ and Zn), $X = (Cl, Br)$, $HL =$ neutral ligand and $n = 0-3$ or $M(HL)_2 X_2 \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Co, Cd$ and Mn), $X = Cl$ or Br and $n = 1-3$. Analytical data are reported in Table 1. All the complexes are insoluble in various

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND SOME PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CYANOACETYLHYDRAZIDE COMPLEXES

Compound	M. P.,	Colour	% Calculated			% Found			Molar Conductance in DMF
			Cl or Br	Metal	N ₂ H ₄	Cl or Br	Metal	N ₂ H ₄	
HL	115	White	—	—	32.34	—	—	—	—
Co(HL)Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	185	Pink	22.0	27.3	12.2	22.2	26.8	12.1	11.6
Co(HL) ₂ Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	195	Pink	19.2	17.5	17.4	19.4	16.2	17.6	19.6
Cd(HL)Br ₂ ·3H ₂ O	158	White	28.3	25.7	8.1	27.6	26.4	7.5	30.1
Cd(HL) ₂ Br ₂ ·3H ₂ O	165	White	31.1	21.5	12.6	30.5	21.4	12.2	30.3
[Cd(HL)Cl.H ₂ O]Cl.H ₂ O	185	White	22.8	35.6	10.1	22.3	35.3	10.6	140.6
[Cd(HL) ₂ Cl.H ₂ O]Cl	145	White	17.8	28.4	16.0	18.1	30.1	16.6	140.6
Mn(HL) ₂ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	above 280	Yellow	21.2	15.6	17.9	20.7	16.1	18.7	23.6
Mn(HL) ₂ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	above 280	Yellow	29.6	22.1	12.6	29.2	22.6	13.2	45.6
Zn(HL) ₂ Cl ₂	220	White	19.2	21.2	—	19.5	21.9	—	30.7

HL = Cyanoacetylhydrazide.

common solvents including water and methanol, but easily soluble in DMF.

Electrical conductivity :

The molar conductance values in DMF at the concentration 10^{-3} M exhibits low values of Λ_m support non-electrolytes in DMF, except the cadmium complexes which have the value $140.6 \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{M}^{-1}$, characteristic for 1:1 type complex.

The conductometric titration curves were obtained by titration of 10 ml 0.001M solutions of Co(II), Cd(II), Mn(II) and Zn(II) against 0.01M ligand solution. Curves drawn between conductances of the solutions and the number of ml of cyanoacetylhydrazide solution showed continuous decrease in conductance with successive addition of the ligand. Moreover, the curves exhibited one or more breaks at certain molar ratios of ligand to metal. The position of the break denoted the composition of the complex formed. Representative curve are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Conductometric titration curves for (a) CoCl_2 , (b) NiCl_2 and (c) MnCl_2 with Cyanoacetylhydrazide

Spectrophotometric studies :

Visible spectra of Co(II) solution shows blue shift of the λ_{max} with increasing concentration of CAH. The stoichiometries of the complex were determined by the methods of Jones⁵, Job⁶, Asmus⁷ and Bent⁸ which gave evidence for the formation of stable complex in simple ratio.

Spectrophotometric studies on the complexes of Co(II) with CAH was performed in order to show

the possibility of applying the reaction for the micro-determination of Co(II). On plotting the absorbance values vs concentration indicates that Co(II) obeys Beer's law up to 2.4×10^{-3} M.

The value of the apparent formation constants for Co(II) complex calculated from the molar ratio and continuous variation methods are 3.8×10^4 and 0.57×10^4 respectively. Both methods gave concordant results.

Electronic spectra :

Co(II)-CAH complex shows a band around 500 nm due to the transition ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ expected for octahedral Co(II) complexes⁹. The electronic spectra of Co(II) complex both in solid phase and in solution are typical of an octahedral stereochemistry.

Infrared Spectra :

The I. R. spectrum of cyanoacetylhydrazide has been discussed by Mashima¹⁰. The results are provided in Table 2.

$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ occurring at 1698 cm^{-1} and amide III at 1258 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of cyanoacetylhydrazide are shifted to lower and higher values respectively in the spectra of the complexes. Thus, a negative shift in the carbonyl stretching frequency and a positive shift in amide III band strongly suggest coordination via carbonyl oxygen.

A positive shift in $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ in the spectra of the complexes indicates that the nitrogen is not involved in coordination. Also, the $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ occurring at 2265 cm^{-1} are shifted in all complexes to lower values. It seems that a stable six membered ring with the metal ion and the ligand have taken place. These results indicate a structure of the type I.

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENT OF IMPORTANT FREQUENCIES (CM^{-1}) OF (CAH) AND ITS COMPLEXES

Compound	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$	Amide I	Amide II	Amide III
HL	3180 vs, 3020 m, 2970 s	2265 vs	1690 vs	1534 m, 1464 s	1258 m
$\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3290 vs, 3230 m, 3150 w	2255 w	1670 s	1570 s	1260 w
$\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3230 s, 3200 s, 3130 m	2250 m	1670 s	1580 s	1265 m
$\text{Cd}(\text{HL})_2\text{Br}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3260 s, 3220 s, 3180 s, 3050 m	2240 s	1670 s	1540 m	1280 w
$\text{Cd}(\text{HL})_2\text{Br}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3240 s, 3200 s, 3140 s, 3070 m	2260 s	1670 s	1540 m	1270 w
$[\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	3260 s, 3180 m, 3140 w, 3100 m	2220 s	1660 s	1540 w	1265 w
$[\text{Co}(\text{HL})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{Cl}$	3280 s, 3210 s, 3160 m, 3100 m	2240 s	1670 s	1550 m	1270 m
$\text{Mn}(\text{HL})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	3240 m, 3160 s, 3120 s, 3060 w	2220 m	1660 s	1540 m	1260 w
$\text{Mn}(\text{HL})_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	3280 s, 3200 m, 3170 s, 3050 m	2240 s	1670 s	1550 s	1270 w

In support of this suggestion we have examined the I.R. spectra of the complexes and have found that N-M frequency of $-C \equiv N \rightarrow M$ group appears [¹¹] in the region 600-800 cm^{-1} .

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